

CARBON NANOTUBES FOR PROPERTY ENHANCEMENT OF EPOXY AT CRYOGENIC ENVIRONMENTS

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Abstract: In the outer space, composite structures are always subject to cyclic thermal stress in which one surface of the structures facing to the Sun experiences temperature over 393 K while an opposite side is 173 K. Besides, the structures may also suffer from damages due to meteoroid attack, in which many tiny particles left over from the formation of the solar system and they are travelling at very high speed to cause serious impact and abrasion onto the structures. In the new Ares V Cargo Launch Vehicle (for the Mar's mission) designed by National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA), the core fuel storage tank will be made by using polymer-based composites and many materials science and engineering research have been conducted to better understand the behavior of these materials at cryogenic condition. In view of all aforementioned problems, composites used at the high attitude (at the level above the Troposphere) should be able to maintain high strength at low temperature environment. Epoxy-based composites are very popular for making advanced composites due to their high strength and chemically-inert properties, making them excellent to be used as aircraft and aerospace structural materials. However, epoxy normally behaves very brittle and therefore, loss of its toughness and impact performance at low temperature. Besides, due to their low energy dissipatability at low temperature, any impact imposed onto its structures would cause delamination and debond at an interface between reinforced fibre and matrix. Many studies have addressed that the use of single-walled (SWNTs) and multi-walled carbon (MWNTs) nanotubes could enhance the mechanical properties of polymer-based composites. However, interfacial bonding properties are always an issue as it would affect the efficiency and effectiveness of stress transfer in the composites. This paper addresses the viability of using coiled carbon nanotubes (CCNT) and randomly-oriented nanoclay-supported nanotubes (NSCNT) to enhance the mechanical properties of epoxy resin at the cryogenic environment. The results obtained from experimental fundings have shown that these nano-reinforcements could effectively enhance the property of epoxy due to their i) surface configuration which could induce the mechanical interlocking between the reinforcements and surrounding matrix and ii) the residual stress due to the shrinkage of the epoxy at low temperature environments.

Keywords: Cryogenic; Nanotubes; Mechanical Properties

1 Introduction

Fibre reinforced polymer-based (FRP) composites have been used extensively in all engineering applications since the last three decades. These composites are made up of soft matrix and high strength fibre to achieve superior mechanical, thermal, electrical and damping properties with their density only one-third of Aluminum. These properties are governed by the excellent interfacial-bonding characteristic between the fibre and matrix. Besides, they can form very complicated shapes with tailored fibre orientations to suit different engineering applications. The versatility of manufacturing processes (hand layup, resin transfer moulding (RTM), resin diffusion, vacuum assisted RTM, autoclave prepreg layup and others), making them readily to be employed for different types of engineering components depending on the quality level required. In the aircraft engineering industries, recent development of Boeing 787 and Airbus A350 use over 45% and 55% of FRP composites, respectively as their primary and secondary components. Although these composites have been used for many years in domestic and civil engineering industries, their endurance at low temperature environments may be an issue as both polymer matrix and bonding interface may experience of brittleness in nature.

In the outer space, coupling effects may exist due to extreme environments, such as low atmospheric pressure, ultra-violet (UV) degradation, atomic oxygen attack, micrometeoroid impact and thermal fatigue of structures. All space structures have to be survived at temperature below 77 K (commonly called at “cryogenic environment”). For spacecraft structures, satellites or cryogenic tanks of launch vehicles always suffer toughness degradation due to the formation of micro-cracks or inner-layer delamination [1]. For the low calorific energy to volume ratio of cryogenic liquid fuels for vehicles and rockets make the pressurized tanks large and heavy when made of metallic materials [2]. For the future re-entry launch vehicles, it also needs to minimize their structural weight in order to increase the capability of carrying more testing equipment and use less fuels (liquid hydrogen and oxygen). Therefore, cryogenic composite or hybrid composite (metal/FRP) fuel tanks can be a promising solution [3]. Due to the increasing use of advanced composites, adhesively bonded joints are then used in many structural components for cryogenic tanks, such as in lobe-to-lobe joints, skirt-to-tank joints and for attaching stringers and ring frames. In practice, delamination in a composite is less severe than the failure at a bonded region and its results in falling off a component completely away from the main structure. For the fuel tanks, polymer materials used for space applications must possess good mechanical and physical properties at cryogenic temperatures such as liquid helium (4.2K), liquid hydrogen (20 K), liquid nitrogen (77 K) and liquid oxygen (90 K) temperatures, etc., to meet the high requirements by the cryogenic applications.

The use of nanoparticles as nano-reinforcements for polymers and polymer-based composites have been reported frequently in the past ten years on the success to enhance their properties as compared with a pristine status. However, most of these works are focused on the room temperature condition and fewer were designed for low temperature or cryogenic environments. At low temperature, the polymers would experience in brittle nature, which cause the decrease of their toughness. The differential coefficients of thermal expansion (CTEs) between the nanoparticles, matrix and fibre also easily induce micro-cracks along the bonding lines and delaminations between inner layers.

In recent research, nanoclay, carbon nanotubes (CNTs) and nanoclay-support nanotubes were used as reinforcements for polymer-based composites and many remarkable results were found experimentally. In certain extent, the type of CNTs would also affect the final properties of composites as incomplete load transfer may be resulted due to a weak van der Waals interaction between the layers inside multi-walled nanotubes (MWNTs). Poor bonding may also be another critical factor that would cause sliding of CNTs inside a composite structure. In such circumstance, the CNTs may induce many cavities inside the structure, and thus prolong microcracks once a tensile load is applied. In this paper, the use of nano-particles as nano-reinforcements for polymers and polymer-based composites is detailedly discussed. Some phenomena are explained to provide a better understanding of stress transfer mechanism at low temperature and cryogenic environments.

2 Low Temperature and Cryogenic Environments

FRP composites are designed for structures, which are required to be high strength and lightweight, for many engineering applications. The composites are comprised of soft polymer matrix and high strength fibre, which is commonly in a brittle nature. In low velocity impact, soft matrix would play a role of cushion to take energies acted externally while fibre aims at absorbing load applied to the composites. In the past, most literatures focused on the development of composites that are served at room temperature environment. The differential coefficients of thermal expansion (CTEs) may not play a critical role, as the expansion rate is small in all substituents. However, at extremely low temperature and critical environments, the shrinkage of composites may induce defects at different interfaces as all substituents would have different expansion rates. Ohtani et al [4] have addressed that cryogenic temperature had a negative effect on the impact resistance of polymer-based composites when they are subjected to a medium velocity impact. At such temperature range, the properties of polymers would be changed from their ductile nature toward brittle, which makes them the energy absorbability becoming lower as compared with their room temperature status. Their results also showed that damage saturation effect once an impact projectile velocity reached ballistic velocity. At that velocity, temperature had no effect on the severity of damage of the composites.

For the toughness resistance, Melcher et al. [5] found that the failure of composite adhesively bonded joints were in a slip-stick fracture mode, where the crack would suddenly propagate and then subside in a repetitive pattern at a cryogenic environment. As aforementioned, the change in polymer's properties would result in reducing the fracture toughness of the composites at this environment. Kalarikkal SG [6] has reported that the critical energy release rates, G_{IC} of polymer-based composites at different fibre orientations were reduced at cryogenic temperature and the failure pattern was similar to Melcher's finding. However, he discovered that by adding some nano-particle would help enhance the fracture toughness of composites by 97% and approximately 53% at room and cryogenic temperatures respectively. The cooling speed of testing specimens would affect the final fracture toughness measurement as thermal shock may deteriorate the properties of composites due to matrix cracking. To have a better understanding of the polymer at cryogenic condition, Figure 1 show the stress-strain curves of Polyphenylene sulfide (PPS) film at different temperature environment [7]. Under the microscopic observation, it was seen that a multiwalled-nanotube (MWNT) was coated by a layer of epoxy at cryogenic condition. However, pullout failure of MWNT was observed for the test conducted at room temperature. It was due to the shrinkage of epoxy, which provided further champing load onto the MWNT's surface. Kim et al. [8] have

addressed that the stiffness and strength of carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP) composites have contrarious effects.

Figure 1. Stress-strain curves of Polyphenylene sulfide (PPS) film at different temperature environment [7].

The stiffness increased with decreasing the temperature of testing environment, while the strength decreased. It was speculated that the brittleness of fibres inside the composites had a major influence on the stiffness increase at low temperatures. By increasing the number of loading cycles, the stiffness decreased with decreasing the temperature while the strength increased. The strength increase was governed by the contraction of matrix, which helped increase the interfacial bonding strength in the composites. Yu et al. [9] have conducted a comprehensive study to examine the mechanical properties of chopped glass fibre reinforced polyurethane foam (PUF) at cryogenic condition. It was found that increasing the amount of chopped fibre into PUF resulted in increasing the compressive strength at cryogenic temperature (120 K), which was a similar phenomena for the tensile property test. The increase of strength in a foam structure was due to the micro-buckling and bridging effects of chopped fibres. Since foam is a relatively weak structural material, it would not influence significantly to the response of temperature. It therefore the chopped played a key role to control the properties of composites at low temperature condition. Such property enhancement also benefits to the interlaminar shear strength (ILSS), which is a key parameter to ensure good bonding between layers of composite structures. Since the delamination may cause stiffness loss, local stress concentration and local instability in the structures, an attention should be paid on this issue if the structures are used at low temperature. Sethi et al. [10] have found that the ILSS of glass/epoxy and carbon/epoxy composites increased with decreasing the temperature down to 173 K from 373 K. Fibre breakage was seen in the micrographs for the glass/epoxy composite tested at 173 K. Roy and Benjamin [11] have pointed out that in the cryogenic composite fuel tanks, the permeation of cryogenic fuel would be caused due to transverse matrix cracks in conjunction with the inter-ply delaminations, and thus form an intersecting network of passage. In their finite element model (FEM), the correlation among the thermos-mechanical loading, delamination length, temperature and permeability based on the Darcy's law for isothermal, viscous flow of gases through porous

media, is developed. The Darcy's law was used to determine the flow rate through a porous material is given by:

$$U = C_{Total} \Delta P \quad (1)$$

where U is the mass flow rate through the material in the thickness direction, C_{Total} is the total conductance of the material in the thickness direction, ΔP is the total pressure differential across the material thickness. At cryogenic environment, the difference of CTEs of fibre and matrix for a composite system would greatly affect the gas permeation rate due to the contraction of materials, formation of microcracks at the bonding interface and also induced residual tensile stress imposed into the system. There is no surprised that the gas permeability would be affected at low temperature condition as the formation of microcracks is somehow unavailable, particular at a sudden change in temperature condition.

Lee et al. [12] conducted lap joint shear tests for metal and composite samples. It was found that the adhesive shear stress increased with decreasing the temperature (from 293 K down to 110 K). As indicated in Fig. 1, the elastic modulus of polymer increases with decreasing the temperature. Lau et al. [13-14] have studied theoretically on the adhesive shear stress of a composite-bonded system, it is shown that the maximum adhesive shear stress ($\tau_{a,max}$) and peel off stress ($\sigma_a^z(z)$) are directly proportional to the Elastic moduli of adhesive and composite plates (Figure 2).

As referred to the results obtained from Lee et al. and Sethi et al., it is reasonable to see that the maximum shear increases with the temperature drops as the moduli of composite samples and adhesive layer (E_a) increase.

$$\tau_{a,max} = C_1 + \eta_o \quad (2)$$

where

$$C_1 = \frac{6G_a R_b d}{E_c t_a \omega h^2 \beta} \tanh\left(\frac{\beta l}{2}\right) \quad (3)$$

and

$$\sigma_a^z(x) = \frac{E_a}{t_a} \left\{ \begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{2\lambda^3} \left\{ \frac{(\omega t_p)^2}{2I_p} (C_1 + \eta_o) - 2H_2 \lambda^3 - \frac{\xi_{v1}}{E_c I_c} - \frac{\beta^3}{4\lambda^4 + \beta^4} (4\lambda^4 \xi_{v2} + \xi_{v3}) \right\} e^{-\lambda x} \cos(\lambda x) - \\ & \frac{1}{2\lambda^2} \left(\frac{\beta^2}{4\lambda^4 + \beta^4} \left(\frac{4\lambda^4}{E_c I_c} \left(\frac{\omega h}{2\beta^3} C_1 \right) - \frac{C_1 \beta (\omega t_p)^2 A_{11}^{-1}}{2I_p} \right) \frac{1}{E_c I_c} \left(R_b d - \frac{\omega h C_1}{2\beta} \right) e^{-\lambda x} \sin(\lambda x) + \right. \\ & \left. + K_1 \xi_{v1}(x) + K_2 \xi_{v2} e^{-\beta x} + K_3 \xi_{v3} e^{-\beta x} + \right. \\ & \left. \frac{1}{E_c I_c} \left\{ \frac{1}{6} R_b x^3 + \frac{\omega h}{2\beta^3} C_1 e^{-\beta x} - \frac{\omega h}{12} \eta_o x^3 + \frac{1}{2} D x^2 + F x + G \right\} \right) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (4)$$

3. Nanoparticle Reinforced Composites

Since the increasing use of polymer-based composites for low temperature structural members have increased in the past years and many issues in relation to the deterioration of their mechanical and structural properties have been reported. Studies on mixing different nanoparticles to strengthen the properties of polymers and composites at cryogenic temperature have emerged recently and many remarkable results were found. Graphene nanosheets [15], Montmorillonite (commonly called “nanoclay”)[16], carbon nanotubes [17-19] and metal powders [20] were used by different research groups to investigate their feasibility of enhancing the properties of composites.

In principle, the purpose of using the nano-particles is similar to those of the use of macro-scale fibres but the reinforcement mechanism is in the relatively small scale. At low temperature environment, shrinkage of surrounding matrix not only imposes compressive stress onto the particles, and thus enhances the interfacial bonding strength of a composite system. However, another possible scenario is the change their geometry (Figure 5), which enhances the bonding strength of nano-reinforcement and therefore, higher strength was observed in the experiments.

Graphene sheets were demonstrated as one of the good nano-reinforcements for polymer-based composites as their planar configuration can provide interlocking mechanism to polymer chains inside the composites [15]. At low temperature, shrinkage of polymers would induce compressive forces added onto the ends which may generate buckling effect to the sheets. However, due to high strength of the sheets, they can then be used to strength the polymers during low temperature condition. It was found that the Young Modulus of graphite/epoxy composites increased with increasing the amount of graphene content up to 0.5 wt%. At the cryogenic environment (77 K), the Modulus measured was double to that measured at room temperature condition [Figure 2]. It was also seen that the control of dispersion is somehow difficult when the amount of graphene sheets increased, agglomeration may be resulted.

Montmorillonite (MMT), commonly called “nanoclay” is another good choice that is used as nano-reinforcement for polymer-based composites. Similar to graphene sheets, it exists in a planner structural form but different layers of nanoclay are stacked together. The perfect way is to separate them by the means of sonication to form intercalated or exfoliated structures. These can be measured by their d-spacing through X-Ray diffraction (XRD) technique. In some extent, chemically-treated nanoclay would help develop these structures in polymer-based materials. Yang et al. [16] have found that the tensile strength and modulus increased when the temperature of MMT/epoxy composites decreased. The modulus increased with increasing the amount of MMT. However, their impact strength decreased at low temperature condition as expected. The glass transition temperature (T_g) was affected by the existence of MMT. T_g is primary dependent on chain flexibility, molecular weight, branching/crosslinking and so on. By adding the MMT into the polymers would restrict the mobility of polymer chains, which may require more energy input to separate their bonds. Thus, T_g of resultant MMT/polymer composites increased.

Lau et al. [17] have found that the use of coiled nanotubes (CCNTs) and nanoclay-support nanotubes (NSCNTs) can enhance the strength of polymer-based composites due to their tailored geometrical patterns. Many studies have criticized poor bonding interface may exist between nanotubes and surrounding matrix, by using these types of nanoparticles could enhance their bonding efficiency, particle at low temperature conditions. Besides, by using these nanotubes, it would avoid agglomeration among nanotubes in the composites (Figure 2). The mechanical properties of epoxy-based composites were enhanced as shown in Table 1.

Figure 2. Coiled carbon nanotube

Wt% of CCNT	Vicker's hardness			Young's modulus		
	RT	77 K	% increase	RT	77 K	% increase
0	0.23	0.31	35	5.0	7.1	42
1	0.28	0.36	28	5.3	7.5	41
2	0.31	0.38	23	5.9	7.9	34
3	0.35	0.41	17	7	8.9	27

Table 1. Mechanical properties of CCNT reinforced epoxy composites at room temperature and 77 K.

4. Conclusion

In this paper, a review on using nanotubes as nano-reinforcement for polymer-based composites as low temperature environments is given. Coiled and nanoclay-support nanotubes provide better bonding strength as compared with straight type nanotubes due to their unique surface configurations. At low temperature condition, shrinkage of polymers would introduce additional compressive stress onto the surface of nanotubes, and thus enhance their bonding strength. Appropriately mixing these nano-structural materials would achieve better strengthening effect in the composites.

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